

Leipzig Institute for Meteorology

University of Leipzig

Master Thesis

Improvement of retrieval algorithms for determining
temperature profiles over the Atlantic

Tobias Doktorowski

2876291

First supervisor: Jun.-Prof. Bernhard Pospichal

Second supervisor: Prof. Andreas Macke

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Abstract

Das Ziel dieser Arbeit war die Verbesserung vorhandener Retrieval-Algorithmen zur Ableitung von Temperaturprofilen über dem Atlantik mit Hilfe des Mikrowellenradiometers HATPRO.

Zur Verbesserung wurden als Eingangsdaten keine Radiosondenstation auf Inseln oder an der Küste genutzt, sondern wurde die Datengrundlage mit Hilfe von Radiosonden, welche vom deutschen Forschungseisbrecher Polarstern und von Containerschiffen aus gestartet wurden, erstellt.

Es wird gezeigt, dass der Algorithm *all_homogen* auf Basis von Radiosonden aus allen Klimazonen, ausgenommen der Polarzonen, die besten Ergebnisse zeigt. Retrievals, die für spezielle Klimazonen entwickelt wurden, konnten nicht immer überzeugen und wurden in den meisten Fällen vom Algorithmus *all_homogen* übertroffen.

Im Vergleich zu den bereits vorhandenen Retrievals schneidet *all_homogen* immer besser ab und schafft es die meteorologischen Bedingungen besser einzufangen.

Abstract

The aim of this thesis was the improvement of already existing retrieval algorithms for determining temperature profiles over the Atlantic by using the microwave radiometer HATPRO.

To improve the algorithms, no radiosondes of island or coastal stations were used, but radiosondes of the German research icebreaker Polarstern and of cargo vessels.

It will be shown that the algorithm *all_homogen*, which is based on radiosondes from all climatic zones except polar regions, delivers the best results. Retrievals which were developed for specific climatic conditions couldn't always convince and will be outweighed in most of the cases .

In comparison to the present retrievals, *all_homogen* showed the best performance and was able to capture the meteorological conditions better.

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1 Introduction

Trends of vertical profiles of atmospheric temperature are an important indicator of climatic change, due to different climate forcing mechanisms exhibit distinct vertical warming and cooling patterns (Raju et al., 2014). To achieve better trends better measurements of current temperature profiles are important. On the one hand low error values are needed and on the other hand more measurements are needed.

Usually, meteorological measurements are only carried out by land stations. So only data sets from islands or coastal stations are available for measurements over the ocean. This can also be seen in fig. 1.1, where regular radiosonde launches are shown. Because of different conditions over land, we usually can't determine the real conditions over the ocean. When satellite measurements are used, it is possible to determine meteorological conditions over the ocean. But usually it is hardly possible to get the information about the conditions within the marine boundary layer (Wood et al., 2015). Ship-borne measurements are the only way to get these informations over the Atlantic. To enlarge the data base for climate and weather models many cargo vessels carry out standard meteorological measurements including daily radio soundings. The obtained data sets in combination with measurements from research vessels make it possible to get more informations over the Atlantic and within the marine boundary layer.

One example is the German research vessel *Polarstern*, which is part of the Alfred Wegener Institute Bremerhaven. Usually the expeditions of *Polarstern* take place in the polar regions. But to reach these regions *Polarstern* needs to carry out transfer ways, on which meteorological informations over the Atlantic can be obtained. These ship-borne measurements are a flexible way to close the gap between satellite and land measurements. Within the scope of Atlantic transfers, which occur twice a year, the Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research performs different measurement within the OCEANET project (Macke et al., 2010) to get information about the solar warming of oceans, the gas exchanges between atmosphere and ocean and biological processes. One big advantage is the crossing of multiple climate zones and different ocean currents, like the warm Brazilian current or the cold Canary current. This makes it possible to capture different conditions in just a few weeks. Since 1983 radio soundings and since 2007 microwave radiometer measurements are carried out on board of *Polarstern*. Furthermore radiation and energy fluxes (Bumke et al., 2014; Macke et al., 2014), aerosols (Kanitz et al., 2013) and clouds (Brückner et al., 2013, 2014) are aims of the research. One of the research interests why

Polarstern carries out meteorological measurements on these transfers is the cooling effect of stratocumulus clouds, which are formed by the inversion on top of the low laying marine boundary layer.

It is usually located in around 500 to 1500m height in the trade wind zone. It is created by the Hadley cell, which transports ascending air masses from the inner tropical convergence zone to the northern tropic where the air masses are descending and getting warmer. Moist and cool airmasses along the western coasts of the continents are caused by cold ocean currents from higher latitudes as well as coastal upwelling. Together with the warm downward branch of the Hadley circulation they form a very stable temperature inversion, which can be seen in the radio sounding in fig. 1.2. At top of the maritime boundary layer stratocumulus clouds are often present. A high ratio of incoming solar radiation is reflected and so the radiation budget at the surface is influenced. The more stratocumulus clouds are formed the stronger is the cooling effect. (Kraus, 2007)

The aim of this work is to show how temperature profiles are determined through microwave radiometer measurements and to improve the old retrieval algorithms or rather develop new ones. The new retrievals are developed for different climate zones to fit better for the specific conditions. It will be shown that the universal algorithm, which includes all climate regions except the polar ones, mostly provides the best results.

Figure 1.1: Network of radiosondes worldwide; yellow dots represent stations, where regular soundings are carried out (Laing and Evans, 2011)

Figure 1.2: Sounding, 25.03.2014, 12UTC, Polarstern cruise PS83 – ANT-XXIX/10, red line=temperature, blue line=dewpoint, modified

2 Basics and theory

2.1 Electromagnetic spectrum

The interaction of atmospheric gases and hydrometeors with electromagnetic waves is highly dependent on frequency. There are two atmospheric window regions, where the attenuation of radiation by atmospheric constituents is low. Figure 2.1 shows the transmissivity of the atmosphere for incoming radiation. The axis of abscissae shows on the one hand the frequency of this radiation and on the other hand the wavelength as logarithmic scale. The axis of ordinates is also a logarithmic scale and shows the attenuation of the incoming radiation. The higher the values of attenuation the higher the optical thickness of the atmosphere for the corresponding frequency or wavelength range. The visual range from 300 to 700 nm features a real low attenuation which is one of the reasons why humans are able to see in this range. Also low attenuation shows the infrared zone at a wave length of $10\ \mu\text{m}$ and the radio wave zone which wave lengths range from 10 cm to 10 m.

Figure 2.1: Electromagnetic spectrum, Transmittance of the atmosphere for electromagnetic waves as a function of wavelength or frequency, both axes with logarithmic scales (Crewell, Crewell)

The microwave range, which varies from 10 to 300 GHz, is the important part for this thesis. In fig. 2.1 it is possible to see two absorption lines of H_2O at 22.235 and 183 GHz and two absorption bands of O_2 at 60 and 118 GHz. The microwave radiometer measurements which are used in this thesis are using the frequency ranges at 22 and 60 GHz. These ranges are also shown in fig. 2.2 where the absorption characteristics of oxygen,

water vapour, clouds and the sum of these three are plotted. The extinction equals the absorption as the scattering can be neglected for microwave radiation. Area A indicates the frequency range which is used for humidity profiling by microwave radiometers. This is due to the local maximum of the absorption coefficient of water vapour Whereas area B is used for temperature profiling. The absorption in band B (51-58 GHz) is nearly only caused by oxygen. The concentration and distribution of oxygen is well-known and so the absorption only depends on the temperature of the atmosphere. Seven different frequencies are used in the described interval B. These frequencies are able to gain differing deep insights of the atmosphere. The incoming radiation, which is detected by a ground-based receiver, originates at 58 GHz from the lowest 500 m to 1000 m height whereas at 51.2 GHz informations are derived from the whole atmosphere.

Figure 2.2: Modelled atmospheric extinction in the microwave spectrum for a cloudy atmosphere, cloudbase=900 hPa, liquid water content= 0.2 g m^{-3} extinction coefficients of oxygen (red), of hydrogen (green), cloud (blue), sum of these three (black) as function of the frequency , A=frequency range for humidity profiling, B=range for temperature profiling (B) (Pospichal, 2015)

2.2 Radiative transfer

By definition, no body can feature a higher emission than a black body at a given temperature T and wavelength λ . This emission is described by Planck's law:

$$B_\nu(T) = \frac{2 h \nu^3}{c^2} \frac{1}{\exp\left(\frac{h\nu}{kT}\right) - 1} \quad (2.1)$$

This is true in a non-scattering medium for frequencies below 100 GHz (Janssen, 1993). Where ν is the frequency, T the temperature, h the Planck constant, c the speed of light and k the Boltzmann constant (Kraus, 2007). By using series expansion $\exp(x) = 1 + x + \dots$ and because of $h\nu \ll kT$ the exponential function can be simplified in the following way:

$$B_\nu(T) = \frac{2 h \nu^3}{c^2} \frac{1}{\frac{h\nu}{kT} + 1 - 1} \quad (2.2)$$

$$B_\nu(T) = \frac{2 \nu^2 k T}{c^2} \quad (2.3)$$

That is also called Rayleigh-Jeans approximation (Simmer, 1994). Especially for the microwave range the error of this approximation is negligible (Stogryn, 1975). If this equation is solved for the temperature the Planck-equivalent brightness temperature can be calculated:

$$T_{\nu B} = \frac{B_\nu c^2}{2 \nu^2 k} \quad (2.4)$$

The brightness temperature corresponds to the physical temperature a body would have, if it was a black body. Therefore the maximum brightness temperature can only be the physical temperature.

The brightness temperature for a passive, ground-based receiver, like the microwave radiometer, can be calculated as follows (Janssen, 1993):

$$T_B = T_{B_{cos}} \exp(-\delta) + \int_0^\infty T(s) \alpha(s) \exp\left(-\int_0^s \alpha(s') ds'\right) ds \quad (2.5)$$

The first summand describes the attenuation of the cosmic background radiation $T_{B_{cos}} = 2.736 \pm 0.017$ K through the optical thickness $\delta = \int_0^\infty \alpha(s) ds$. Here, α is the volume absorption coefficient. The second summand describes the atmospheric part which includes the emission of atmospheric gases and hydro meteors. It is hard to determine this part,

Figure 2.3: Normalized weighting functions (left) and normalized difference weighting functions (right) (Rose and Czekala, 2014)

so weighting functions are introduced:

$$W(\nu, z) = \alpha(\nu, z) \exp\left(-\int_z^\infty \alpha(\nu, z') dz'\right) \quad (2.6)$$

This weighting function is applied to the calculation of the brightness temperatures:

$$T_B(\nu) = \int_0^\infty W(\nu, z) T(z) dz \quad (2.7)$$

So, the incoming radiation at the radiometer is the sum of the values of the different heights multiplied with the weighting function $W(\nu, z)$. With help of the weighting function it is possible to determine the height from which the measured information originates. This can also be seen in fig. 2.3. On the left are the normalized weighting functions shown. The conclusion is the lower the frequency the higher the height where more informations are gathered. This is also pointed out on the right side of fig. 2.3. Here the difference of neighbored frequencies is calculated. This makes it possible to gather the informations from greater heights and to improve the measurements.

Now the task is to determine the temperature profile $T(z)$ which is linked with $\alpha(\nu, z)$. But this leads to the inverse problem of remote sensing.

2.3 Inverse problem of remote sensing

The inverse problem of remote sensing can be described by an analogy from Bohren and Huffman (1983); if you know the size and the colour of a dragon then you can deduce the dragon track from these informations. But if only the dragon track is the known quantity then it is really difficult to determine the colour or other details of the dragon. This problem can be translated to remote sensing; for an existing temperature profile it is no problem to determine the spectral remote sensing measurement using a radiative transfer model. If only the spectral measurement is available, like here in this master thesis, it is difficult to determine the temperature profile. To solve this problem an inverse modelling is carried out.

Here m measurements y_i are given with $i=0,1,2,\dots,m$, like e.g. measurements for m different wavelengths. But n parameters x_j with $j=0,1,2,\dots,n$ are wanted. These parameters correspond to e.g. the temperature in different height levels. Furthermore physical interaction regulations are given. They include the absorption cross section and the description of wave propagation by the Maxwell's equations and the radiative transfer equations. The interaction regulations are declared as forward model F . So following equation is received:

$$y_i = F(x_j, j = 1, \dots, n) \quad i = 1, \dots, m \quad (2.8)$$

However the wanted equation is:

$$x_j = T(y_i, i = 1, \dots, m) \quad j = 1, \dots, n \quad (2.9)$$

By using inverse modelling a method to determine T has to be found. But the inversion of the forward model with the following scheme is not as easy as it seems:

$$\vec{y} = F(\vec{x}) \equiv \bar{F}\vec{x} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \vec{x} = \bar{F}^{-1}\vec{y} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \bar{T} = \bar{F}^{-1}$$

Mostly this inversion is on the one hand error-prone and on the other hand F^{-1} might not be existent because the count of measurements is mostly less than the count of free parameters. So we get an under-determined system of equations with $n \gg m$. Furthermore F^{-1} mostly doesn't exist because of the dependence of F on X_j . So F is a non-linear operator.

One possible solution is the stabilization of the model through redundant measurements. A further possibility lie in the addition of virtual measurements or constraints. The third option uses iterative methods like the 'optimal estimation', where the truth is approximated by the best estimation of the the most probable solution(Kamen and Su, 1999; Löhnert et al., 2008; Rodgers, 2000; Foth et al., 2016).

$$\hat{x}_j = T^*(y_i, i = 1, \dots, m) \quad j = 1, \dots, n \quad (2.10)$$

Here, the free parameters of T^* has to be determined that the following sum will be minimal:

$$\sum_k (x_j - T^*(y_i, i = 1, \dots, m))^2 = \sum_k (x_j - \hat{x}_j)^2 \quad (2.11)$$

x_j is the truth respectively the real measurement and \hat{x}_j is the result of the retrieval. This equation shows that the sum would be zero if the retrieval equals the truth. This would be the result of a perfect algorithm, which is not possible.

2.4 Microwave radiometer HATPRO

Figure 2.4: OCEANET container on research vessel Polarstern, HATPRO is on the lower right

The microwave radiometer which is operated on Polarstern is the Humidity And Temperature PROfiler HATPRO from Radiometer Physics GmbH. It is used for passive determination of self emission of atmospheric parts and the cosmic background radiation. This is realised by 14 channels of the microwave spectrum (Rose et al., 2005). They are separated into seven frequencies from 22.24 GHz to 31.4 GHz according to the absorption line of water vapour and into seven frequencies from 51.3 to 58 GHz according to the ab-

Figure 2.5: Inner structure of HATPRO (Rose and Czekala, 2013)

sorption line of oxygen (Crewell and Lohnert, 2007). HATPRO during the measurement campaign PS98 can be seen in fig. 2.4. The blue radome which makes a third of the surface is only permeable for microwave radiation. On the inside, shown in fig. 2.5, is a scanning parabola antenna which forwards the radiation to a beam splitter which splits the incoming radiation in two frequency ranges. Receiver 1 is for the humidity profiling and receiver 2 for the temperature profiling. On the outside, next to the radome, a blower is installed which reduces the humidity on the radome and prevents the accumulation of ice. Furthermore a infrared radiometer is installed which is used for determining the cloud height. In addition there are a GPS receiver and a rain sensor. During humidity profiling every kind of rain will disturb the measurements whereas during temperature profiling light rain the measurements hardly influences.

2.5 Application

To gain better algorithms a bigger data base has to be found. In this master thesis on the one hand all radiosonde data from the research vessels Polarstern has been used, which can be found on the Pangea website (<https://www.pangaea.de/expeditions/cr.php/Polarstern>). On the other hand the German weather service DWD provided thousands of soundings which were carried out by cargo vessels. After filtering the data set 36 772 radio soundings remain for being processed in the algorithms. Soundings which didn't reach 10 000 m height or had less than ten measurements were skipped. The remaining

Figure 2.6: Schematic presentation of the creation and comparison of new retrieval algorithms, RT=radiative transfer ((Pospichal, 2015), modified)

radiosondes, which can be seen in fig. 2.7, were put into a radiative transfer model, which calculated i.a. brightness temperatures out of the physical temperatures. For the radiative transfer, a non-scattering microwave transfer model based on MWMOD (Simmer, 1994; Fuhrhop et al., 1998) is used. Whereas the oxygen absorption is based on Rosenkranz (1998) and the water vapour absorption on Liebe et al. (1991). This forward model is only valid for non-scattering cases (Marke et al., 2016). Afterwards the data is used to calculate the retrieval algorithms. The respective radiosondes which are used for one particular algorithm are split into test and training data, which is described in fig. 2.6. After splitting up, on the one hand the soundings are put into the radiative transfer model and brightness temperatures T_B are calculated on the other hand just the temperature profiles $T(z)$ are used. For the training data T_B and $T(z)$ are processed in a statistical model with multiple regression and afterwards together with T_B from the test data they form the algorithm. This new algorithm will be compared with the temperature profile from the test data.

Figure 2.7: Filtered radiosondes from Polarstern and cargo vessels

3 Introduction and discussion of new retrieval algorithms

Retrieval	latitude	quantity train / test	characteristic
all	60°S to 60°N	14193 / 13445	-
all_homogen	60°S to 60°N	2621 / 2582	same amount of radiosondes of 10° latitude steps
aequ	10°S to 10°N	556 / 795	-
trop	30°S to 30°N	2849 / 2984	-
trop_wet	30°S to 30°N	1277 / 1523	only IWV > 35 kg m ⁻²
trop_dry	30°S to 30°N	1556 / 1461	only IWV < 35 kg m ⁻²
trade	5°N to 30°N	754 / 762	-
north	30°N to 60°N	10304 / 9309	-
south	60°S to 30°S	1017 / 1162	-

Table 3.1: Details of new retrievals

A total of nine new retrieval algorithms have been created, which are all listed in table 3.1. Measurements of Polarstern are used from 2008 to 2016. For all retrievals a liquid water path threshold of 1 kg m⁻² is chosen. So all cases where this threshold is exceeded can be neglected because of extrem wet or rainy conditions. The retrieval *all* includes sounding from all latitudes from 60°S to 60°N. Therefore all climatic conditions, except polar ones, are included. The same is true for *all_homogen*, but there, the domination of the northern radio soundings is reduced by using the same amount of soundings from every 10° step. The other algorithms are divided according to the corresponding geographical region.

3.1 Comparison of new retrieval algorithms

Because of the different mean temperature profiles in different climatic regions, which is shown in fig. 3.1, it seems to make sense to use different retrievals for different climates. The different meteorological, climatic caused conditions build the framework for retrieval algorithms. Like typical conditions in the south temperate zone, the retrieval for this region underestimates the mean ground temperature for all regions by around 2.6 K. This is due to the used radiosondes for this algorithm. They usually detect lower ground temperatures as in other regions, so the algorithm provides a lower surface temperature. On

RMSE	north	south	tropics	equator	all	trade	mean
all	1.33337	1.74371	1.60692	1.18253	1.5878	1.68996	1.524
aequ	2.13856	3.0342	1.84257	1.18689	2.13348	1.95506	2.0485
trop_all	1.82037	2.54888	2.17673	1.59405	2.17533	1.92072	2.0393
trop_dry	2.0176	2.73595	2.41751	1.9761	2.40107	2.12196	2.2784
trop_wet	2.23979	3.30214	1.69521	1.18049	2.13512	1.70538	2.043
north	1.35896	1.75748	1.7072	1.24064	1.66032	1.80456	1.5882
south	1.4318	1.87198	1.92062	1.4748	1.83569	1.95651	1.7486
all_hom	1.33407	1.76426	1.54368	1.16512	1.54865	1.59656	1.4921
trade	1.75362	2.42114	2.09162	1.55419	2.08685	1.83475	1.957
dar	2.40067	2.71593	2.03611	1.28366	2.25991	2.20614	2.1504
deb	1.5932	1.72861	2.06924	1.36831	1.93969	2.25897	1.8263
mol	1.69295	1.84619	2.27123	1.5612	2.11124	2.37204	1.9758

Table 3.2: RMSE values of all algorithms in different geographical regions from 0 to 2000 m, green to red: low to high RMSE values, north: 30°N to 60°N, south: 60°S to 30°S, tropics: 30°S to 30°N, equator: 10°S to 10°N, all: 60°S to 60°N, trade: 5°N to 30°N and 45°W to 0°E, mean shows mean value of RMSE of one algorithm for all regions

the contrary retrievals for warmer regions, like the equator or tropical zone, overestimate the mean ground temperature for all regions by around 0.6 to 0.8 K. These retrievals show on contrary an underestimation of around 1.7 K at 1000 m. The bias of the algorithms *all* and *all_homogen* stay relatively constant with an underestimation from *all* by 0.5 K and an alternation around zero from *all_homogen* for nearly all heights.

When we take a look at the marine boundary layer of the trade wind zone, which is represented in fig. 3.2, the underestimation of the ground temperature by nearly 3.5 K from retrieval *south* is obvious. *trop_all* and *aequ* show a slightly overestimation of the ground temperature by 0.2 to 0.5 K, which is probably caused by cooler ocean currents, like the canary current, in this region. The retrieval *aequ* shows a big underestimation by around 2 K at 1000 m. All other algorithms show relatively good results with an underestimation by around 0.5 to 1 K from 1000 to 2000 m.

The differences between the various retrievals is getting more clear when the RMSE (root mean square error) is considered like in fig. 3.3. It has to be kept in mind that in fig. 3.3 only error values for the trade wind zone is shown. At ground especially the algorithms

Figure 3.1: Mean temperature difference, Radiosonde is subtracted from HATPRO, in region from 60°S to 60°N

trade, *south*, *trop_all* and *trop_dry* produce error values greater than 2.7 K up to 4.5 K. These larger errors are caused by the different input data sets, which contain non-typical situations for the trade wind zone. But this isn't valid for the *trade* retrieval which is made especially for this region. In contrary to the low BIAS value at ground the RMSE with a value of 2.75 K is comparatively high. This is caused by different ocean currents which are crossed in this region. On the one hand the cold Canary current is present on the one hand the warmer equatorial current is crossed. These differences causes relative high error values at the surface, but from 800 m on, the *trade* retrieval shows the best results. The algorithms *all*, *all_homogen*, *trop_wet* and *aequ* have a RMSE of around 1 K from ground to 500 m height. From 700 m on all algorithms except *aequ* show relatively constant error values of around 2 K, which are getting more expanded when the height is increased.

The RMSE values in the south temperate zone show higher differences between the retrievals and higher RMSE values than in the trade wind zone. Like shown in fig. 3.4 the best results are derived from *all*, *all_homogen*, *north* and *south*. Interestingly the *south* retrieval is the weakest of these four from 1000 m on. This can be due to due to the small

Figure 3.2: BIAS values for trade wind zone from 5°N to 30°N

number of cases of radio soundings which can be used to create the retrieval, compare table 3.1. Typical wet and warm algorithms like *aequ* and *trop_wet* produce high error values exceeding 5 K. Here can also be seen, why it makes sense to use *all_homogen* instead of *all* even though it is showing slightly worse results in this case. The algorithms *north* and *all* are here more or the less the same. That is due to the domination of radio soundings of the north temperate zone in the algorithm *all*.

This effect can also be seen in fig. 3.5, which shows the BIAS values in the south temperate zone. *all* and *north* show nearly the same values, but *all_homogen* shows slightly differences. *Trop_wet* and *aequ* show again that tropic retrievals aren't well suited for the south temperate zone. At surface and from 1000 m height on they overestimate the temperature. However the retrieval *south* shows relatively good results as expected.

But for other regions, *south* isn't well suited. Like in fig. 3.6 it underestimates the surface temperature considerably. At 500 m height the BIAS is for all regions, except south, nearly 0 K. However higher levels show again an underestimation of the temperature. For the south temperate zone it shows a nearly constant BIAS of -0.5 to -1 K up to 1000 m. Afterwards the BIAS changes slowly to +0.5 K. In conclusion south is only usable for the south temperate zone.

Figure 3.3: RMSE values for trade wind zone from 5°N to 30°N

However *all_homogen* shows very good results for all regions, which can be seen both in tab. 3.2 and in fig. 3.7. Except for the southern region, BIAS values are tending between 0 and -0.3 K. Up to 2000 m height the BIAS varies between -1 and 0.5 K for all regions. The RMSE values of table 3.2 make it clear, that *all_homogen* provides overall the best results with a mean RMSE of 1.49 K . Even though *all* shows comparable good results (1.52 K) it is influenced by the measured data of the north temperate zone, so *all_homogen* has to be preferred.

3.2 Comparison with present retrieval algorithms

For the comparison with the previously developed algorithms *deb*, *dar* and *mol* the new retrievals *all*, *all_homogen* and the according algorithm for the considered region. *mol* is based on radio soundings from Lindenberg in Germany and *deb* on radio soundings from De Bilt in the Netherlands. Both are representing more or the less conditions for the north temperate zone. *dar* is based on measurement from Darwin in Australia and represents the moist tropical zone.

Figure 3.4: RMSE values for south temperate zone from 60°S to 30°S

The first thing which attracts attention in fig. 3.8 is the oscillating of the old retrievals, whereas the new retrievals *all* and *all_homogen* show relatively constant BIAS values, which range between -0.7 and 0 K. The highest range shows *mol* with an interval from -3.3 to 1.8 K. However this isn't very surprising because here all measurements between 60°S and 60°N are considered.

In fig. 3.9 only the measurements of the north temperate zone are used for the comparison of the retrievals so the retrieval *north* is also taken into account. *dar* and *deb* show slightly better results, but *all*, *all_homogen* and *north* are more constant and supply clearly better results. The lowest 200 m and from 1300 m on *all_homogen* delivers the best values, whereas *north* shows the best values between 200 and 1300 m. Here again it can also be seen that *all* and *north* are more or the less the same. Surprisingly *dar* shows relatively bad results although it is made for tropical conditions. This can also be seen in fig. 3.10 which shows the RMSE values of this region. Except for the surface *dar* provides the highest RMSE values. Whereas *all*, *all_homogen* and *north* show more or the less the lowest error values. On average *all* and *all_homogen* suit best for the north temperate zone, which can be validated with the entries in table 3.2.

Due to the bad influence and high error values of the dry cases in *trop_all* for further

Figure 3.5: BIAS values for south temperate zone from 60°S to 30°S

investigations *trop_wet* is used. This can be seen in table 3.2; for the tropic region *trop_dry* has an RSME of 2.42 K and *trop_all* 2.18 K whereas *trop_wet* only supplies a value of 1.70 K. However *all_homogen* provides a relative low error with 1.54 K. This good result can also be seen in fig. 3.11. In comparison to other regions *dar* delivers better results with a mean error of 2,04 K but still isn't as good as the new retrievals *all_homogen* and *trop_wet*. When we take a look at the BIAS in fig. 3.11 it can be seen that the old algorithms show bad results where *dar* provides slightly the best values of these three. *all* and *all_homogen* provide relative constant BIAS values between -1 to -0.1 K and *trop_wet* shows a range from -1 to 1 K.

But there is one region where *deb* and *mol* provide relatively good results. The RMSE values are more or the less consistent with the values of the new retrievals which can be seen in fig. 3.14. *deb* is surprisingly showing the best value with 1.73 K whereas *south* has the worst result, excpeting *dar*, with a RMSE of 1.87 K. Also the BIAS values aren't so high like in other regions, which can be validated by fig. 3.13. *deb* is reatively constant from 200 m up to 2000 m height with a BIAS range from -0.7 to -0.1. Even *mol* is showing a more constant course but nonetheless is still oscillating.

Figure 3.6: BIAS values of algorithm *south* in different geographical regions

3.3 Practical suitability

It was expected that it is advantageous to develop different algorithms for different geographical regions or climatic regions. As shown in the previous discussion the retrieval *all_homogen* provides the best results (lowest RMSE values) for nearly all regions. Only in the south temperate zone *all* and *deb* provide better results. But it is only a RMSE difference to *all_homogen* of 0.02 to 0.04 K. The only region where also the specific algorithm shows a better performance is the equator region from 10°S to 10°N. As shown in table 3.2 *all*, *all_homogen*, *trop_wet* and *aequ* deliver very good results. Except for rare special cases *all_homogen* is always the number one choice. Especially during measurement campaigns on research vessel it is important and useful to just use one retrieval instead of many different. But it has to be kept in mind that polar measurements aren't taken in account in this thesis.

Figure 3.7: BIAS values of algorithm *all_homogen* in different geographical regions

Figure 3.8: BIAS values in region from 60°S to 60°N

Figure 3.9: BIAS values in north temperate zone from 30°N to 60°N

Figure 3.10: RMSE values in north temperate zone from 30°N to 60°N

Figure 3.11: BIAS values in the tropics from 30°S to 30°N

Figure 3.12: RMSE values in the tropics from 30°S to 30°N

Figure 3.13: BIAS values in the south temperate zone from 60°S to 30°S

Figure 3.14: RMSE values in the south temperate zone from 60°S to 30°S

4 Influence of elevation scans

Usually HATPRO only measures with a zenith angle of 0.0° because it was assumed that measurements at more angles will be disturbed by the movement of Polarstern. But in fact in only 0.04% of the cases the total inclination of the research vessel exceeds 5.0° (Zoll, 2012). So during the expeditions PS98 and PS102 every 30 minutes elevation scans were carried out. They include additional measurements at 5.4° , 10.2° , 19.2° , 30.0° , 42.0° and 90.0° . For this thesis the measurements were not filtered by the inclination angles of Polarstern due to the lack of ship information data. So larger inclination angles are also included in the following results but should not affect them too much. As shown in the previous chapter the retrieval *all_homogen* provides the best results for all regions, so it is the only retrieval used in the following figures.

Fig. 4.1 shows the comparison of BIAS and RMSE of measurements with and without elevation scans. It can be seen that the BIAS for measurements with elevation scans only ranges between -0.3 and 0.3 K. Whereas without elevation scan the BIAS between -1.3 and 0.9 K ranges. Also the RMSE values are improved and range between 0.6 K at the surface and 1.4 K at 2000 m height. Without elevation scans only a RMSE range from 1.0 to 1.8 K is achieved.

In fig. 4.2 can be seen a comparison of one radiosonde measurement with HATPRO measurements with and without elevation scans. This measurements was carried out in the Bay of Biscay. The radiosonde and the elevation scans measurement are nearly identical. Only between 500 and 1000 m height are a bit larger differences, but nevertheless the measurement without elevation scans shows a high deviation to the radiosonde profile. Even though the elevation scans deliver better results, not every situation is perfectly captured. Like in fig. 4.3, which shows a typical inversion in the trade wind zone. When a strong inversion is formed it doesn't matter if elevation scans are carried out or not. Both measurements can't capture the inversion and show nearly identical profiles.

However it is obvious that elevation scans provide better results in the marine boundary layer and have to be carried out in further measurements even though that typical inversions can't be imaged by current algorithms.

Figure 4.1: Mean RMSE and BIAS values during expeditions PS98 and PS102, used retrieval is *all_homogen*, red=BIAS, green=RMSE, solid=no elevation scans, dotted=elevation scans

Figure 4.2: Comparison of radiosonde (black) and measurements with (red) and without (green) elevation scans, used retrieval is *all_homogen*, coordinates: 45.59°N 8.2°W

Figure 4.3: Comparison of radiosonde (black) and measurements with (red) and without (green) elevation scans, used retrieval is *all_homogen*, coordinates: 14.02°N 23.52°W

5 Summary

Due to the lack of regularly measurements over the Atlantic it is helpful that retrievals for determining temperature profiles with HATPRO are working well and produce only small errors. So it is possible to retrieve good results with few measurements.

The retrievals which are presented in this thesis are based on radiosondes launched by Polarstern and cargo vessels. So all needed climatic conditions are part of the retrievals.

It was expected that each retrieval, which was developed for this thesis, will be the best one for the linked climatic zone. But it was shown that no specific retrievals for different climatic zones are needed. Just one algorithm *all_homogen* is needed to determine temperature profiles in climatic zones between 60N and 60S. It is based on radiosondes from all latitudes between 60N and 60S. It provides in most of the cases the lowest RMSE values.

This makes it possible to use this retrieval during a whole measurement campaign. It is not needed to check which retrieval fits better for a specific situation.

But also this algorithm is still optimisable. On the one hand more radiosondes will provide better results and on the other hand elevation scans with HATPRO should be carried out when possible. It was shown that these elevation scans provide a more accurate result and reduce the RMSE to a minimum. The combination of elevation scans and a better database will improve the new retrieval. In this thesis only temperature profiles were considered, if these retrievals also show a good performance for determining the liquid water path or the liquid water content

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I hereby declare that the thesis submitted is my own unaided work. All direct or indirect sources used are acknowledged as references.

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